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MONITORING SHORELINE CHANGES OF SRI LANKA USING REMOTE SENSING AND GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Shorelines are altering at an accelerating rate due to both human activities and physical phenomena as they represent the interface between the land and water. The primary objective of the study, Monitoring Shoreline Changes on the Coastline Security of Sri Lanka using Remote Sensing and Geographic Information System (GIS) Techniques, is to analyse shoreline changes from 2004 to 2021 using geospatial techniques. Shorelines for years of 2004, 2015 and 2021 were delineated using Landsat 7 and Landsat 8 images. By applying, the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) landmasses were distinguished from water bodies, and shorelines were extracted. The Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) was used to quantify the rate of long-term shoreline changes over 17 years and assess shoreline changes, including Shoreline Change Envelope (SCE), Net Shoreline Movement (NSM) and, End Point Rate (EPR). The DSAS results reveal that the Kalutara region has experienced the greatest natural erosion, while the eastern coastline (Kayankerni area) has undergone the greatest natural accretion (except port city

and other harbors). The highest SCE values, reaching 843 m, were calculated within the eastern coastline. The highest NSM ranges indicative of accretion were recorded as 819 m in the eastern coastline, while the highest ranges indicative of erosion were recorded as -305 m in the western coastline. The calculated EPR of the area was -17.9 m/year. These findings can serve as valuable input data for maintaining the security of coastal zone management and mitigating further anthropogenic and natural threats to coastal habitats in Sri Lanka.

KEYWORDS: *Digital Shoreline Analysis System, End Point Rate, Net Shoreline Movement, Shoreline Change Envelope, Shoreline Changes.*

INTRODUCTION

A shoreline can be defined as the location of the land-water interface in a specific time. Moreover, it is a very dynamic feature that provides an indicator of coastal erosion and accretion (Mohammed E et al., 2018). The effects of various land uses, geological and hydrological dynamic phenomena have made

changes in coastal areas. Among them sediment erosion, transport and deposition have been identified as crucial factors. These changes can be detected in both short and long periods. In general, the processes of marine phenomenon cause a direct impact on the design of the security of the country especially in harbors, marine structures, and coastal management (E Tamassoki et al. 2014).

Security can simply be defined as actions taken to protect individuals, communities and their assets from threats and risks. Additionally, it can be identified as a highly nuanced process that encompasses various aspects including physical security, economic stability, bio diversity and ecosystems, environmental protection and national security, ensuring resilience against natural disasters, crimes, economic disruptions and other potential threats. Therefore, concerns about the consequences of coastal erosion onto security cannot be neglected and the protection of the coastline plays a prominent role in ensuring the safeguard of the nation. Whether its results are short-term or long-term, coastal changes have had a direct impact. Studying coastal changes is very important, especially in matters related to the safety of natural harbors, public safety, and the security of the interior of the country. With the sudden changes experienced over time, due to the factors such as climatic changes, most of the countries became vulnerable, facing enormous security risks to both human and nature.

Sri Lanka's low-lying coastal areas tend to undergo constant changes, with erosion and deposition continuously altering change the shoreline (Narayana, 2016). These changes include both seasonal and permanent shifts (Joseph, 2007). Sri Lanka's coastal regions are densely populated when compared to the inland areas. (Weerakkody, 1996; Berg et al., 1998; Gopalakrishnan et al., 2020) and among them, the southwestern coastal zone can be identified as the most populous (Elizabeth et al, 2005).

Coastal change analysis in Sri Lanka can be regarded as a critical piece of research that addresses the dynamic and complex interactions between natural coastal processes and human activities with regards to the security of the country. According to the Statistical Abstract of 2022, in the Department of Census and Statistics, the island, Republic of Sri Lanka is located in the Indian Ocean between the northern latitude of 5°55' and 9°51' and the eastern longitude of 79°41' to 81°53' and covers an area of 65,610 km². It mainly consists of an elongated pearl-shaped tropical island with a maximum length of 432 km from Dewandara Point in the south to Pedurutuduwa in the north and a maximum width of 224 km from Colombo on the west coast to Kalmunai on the east coast. Several small islands are also scattered along its coast. The coastline stretches approximately 1,790 km and coastline features may include bays, anchorages and natural harbours (Bandara, 1989). Coastal accretion, erosion and sea-level rise are identified as the significant threats to the coastal regions of Sri Lanka. Prominently, these issues often affect the social security, economic security (such as fisheries and tourism), infrastructure protection, urban planning and development, etc. Therefore, this research is very important in aligning future steps ensuring security of Sri Lanka's coastline.

This study investigates coastal changes in the main island of Sri Lanka, aiming to provide sound knowledge of the previous changes that have occurred across the entire coastal region on the main island with a perspective on safeguarding the security. These results can be used to analyse the reasons for erosion and accretion along the coastline and initiate measures for coastal management. When investigating these kinds of dynamics of the shorelines, remote sensing technology and geographic information systems (GIS) are useful tools. Shoreline changes can be investigated over time by comparing of satellite images (De Silva et al., 2021). Advanced remote sensing technologies and GIS are widely used in this research to provide accurate, up-to-date data

on coastal dynamics, enabling more effective policy-making and coastal management strategies.

Given the critical need for effective coastal management to protect infrastructure and communities in coastal areas, primary objective of this research is to monitor the shoreline changes using the multi-temporal medium resolution satellite images, acquired in Sri Lanka from 2004 and 2021 covering 17 years and to provide an analysis of their implications for protection. It comprises with advanced remote sensing technologies with geospatial analysis with Landsat data pre-processed and processed using Google Earth Engine (GEE). This research aims not only to contribute to academic understanding of coastal dynamics, but also to inform policymaking and strategic planning efforts aimed at improving coastal resilience and protection. The researchers seek to develop a robust outline for mitigating the impacts of coastal change in the future. The methodologies used in this study include satellite imagery analysis, processing outputs from Google Earth Engine into the Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS 5.1) in ArcMap, calculate statistical values of coastal changes and GIS mapping of vulnerable coastal areas. The Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) is a freely available software application that works within the Esri Geographic Information System (ArcGIS) software. The DSAS extension generates the rate-of-change statistics for a time series of shorelines. Major statistical outcomes of the DSAS such as Net Shoreline Movement (NSM), Shoreline Change Envelope (SCE), Endpoint Rate (EPR) and Linear Regression Rate (LRR) are used for the interpretation and visualization of shoreline dynamics over time. Finally, this research seeks to provide actionable insights and practical recommendations for policy makers who are involved in coastal management and defence planning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Shorelines are the most dynamic environments on Earth, continuously changing through erosion, deposition, and the action of waves and currents over time (Bird, 2000). The term 'coastline' is often used synonymously with 'shoreline'. Shorelines changes occur both in small ways throughout the day and in large ways over years or decades. A shoreline is defined as the physical boundary between land and water (Boak et al, 2005). Shoreline changes are influenced by various factors, including monsoon winds, wave actions, sediment transportation, sea level rise, tidal movements, and natural disasters such as tsunami, typhoon and human activities (Palamakumbure et al., 2020; Gunasinghe et al., 2021). Thus, shoreline changes the result from both natural and anthropogenic causes, manifesting as either erosion or accretion (Yu et al., 2011). Erosion is the wearing away of soil or rock while accretion is the opposite process.

Therefore, constant shoreline monitoring has become crucial to minimize impact on living and ecological resources, resulting in hazard-effective conservation mechanisms and maintaining the social, economic, and environmental security in the country (Al-Zubieri et al., 2020; Roy et al., 2018). Accurate calculation of shoreline change rates requires continuous and long-term monitoring of shoreline location data (Luijendijk et al., 2018). Combined ground and satellite observations and simulations of Indian Ocean sea level, have identified a clear spatial pattern of sea level rise since the 1960s. According to tide gauge data, the sea level along the coast of the northern Indian Ocean has risen by about 12.9 cm per century (Thasarathan, N.et al, 2023). Coastal communities and developments along Sri Lanka's coastline may be highly vulnerable to both permanent and short-term inundation and/or coastal erosion, making Sri Lanka a one of the hot spots to study in future sea-level change and risk assessments (Palamakumbure, L., 2020)

Understanding coastal dynamics allows for more resilient infrastructure design, protection against erosion and flooding (Wijeratne et al. 2018). To ensure national economic stability and daily operations, it is mandatory to protect infrastructure such as ports and commercial ports, power plants, other business institutions, important national security facilities, agricultural lands, and roads located in both inland and coastal areas. Coastal zones are strategic areas for national security due to their proximity to maritime borders and trade routes. Maintaining the integrity of these coastal zones is critical for preventing illegal activities and ensuring safe maritime operations, promoting nations to implement protocols for their security (Samarakoon, 2016). Sri Lanka, positioned along major sea routes between the West and East, which has strategic importance in the Indian Ocean, making coastal surveillance vital to maintain maritime sovereignty (Bandara, 1989; Samarakoon, 2016). However, during Sri Lanka's internal civil war, significant knowledge gaps emerged due to limited scientific research in the region over the past three-decades (Thasarathan, N. et al, 2023).

In recent years, numerous studies have been conducted to assess the extent and impact of coastal erosion along the eastern, southern, western coastal zones separately. The east coast is home to many critical features, including ports such as Olivil, Trincomalee as well as urbanized areas and tourist destinations such as Nilaveli, Pasikuda and Arugambe, and important conservation areas like Yala and Kumana National Parks. Additionally, high quality mineral deposits are found in locations such as Pulmodei, Verugal and Kokilai (Zoysa et al., 2023). After the end of the civil war in 2009, Sri Lanka underwent rapid urbanization and underwent various large-scale development projects such as Colombo Port City Project, Hambantota Port, and Olivil Port, Coastal Road and Infrastructure Projects implemented in various coastal areas.

As many changes have been caused to the coastline with the mega development projects, variations have been observed with respect to coastal changes within the study area. Despite the significant changes to the coastline from these development projects, a notable gap exists in research on the overall coastal changes across the country. According to the author's knowledge, no recent study has comprehensively analysed the entire coastline of Sri Lanka. Making informed decisions related to national security requires addressing threats to any sector promptly, focusing on the whole country. Therefore, this research aim to fulfil the existing knowledge gap and secure the country from future coastal threats.

METHODOLOGY

The study area selected for the research is the island of Sri Lanka located in the northern part of the Indian Ocean between the northern latitude of 5°55' and 9°51' and the eastern longitude of 79° 41' to 81° 53'. The total land area of the island is approximately 65,610 km² with a coastline about 1,620 km. While Sri Lanka comprises many small islands, this study focuses solely on the mainland.

The methodology of coastal change monitoring in Sri Lanka using remote sensing and GIS techniques consist of four main stages namely data acquisition, preprocessing, processing and calculation of coastal change rate (see figure 1). Coastal changes in the study area were analysed using Landsat satellite images from the years of 2004, 2015 and 2021. These satellite images consist of multispectral images captured by Landsat satellites. The first step in the research was to retrieve data from Landsat 8 and Landsat 7 images from the relevant image collections in Google Earth Engine.

Figure 1: Methodology for Coastal Change Monitoring Using Remote Sensing and GIS Techniques

These images were processed and analysed using Google Earth Engine and Geographic Information System (ArcGIS software) to identify and delineate the shoreline accurately. Then, the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) was applied to enhance the contrast between land and water, facilitating precise shoreline extraction. Following the extraction, a buffer was created to digitize the baseline, forming the initial step for the fourth stage. In a personal geodatabase, all selected coastlines and the digitised baseline were combined into a single feature class.

This research utilised the Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) integrated ArcGIS 10.8 to assess and monitor shoreline changes in the study area. DSAS computes rate-of-shoreline change statistics for a time series of shoreline vector data. Once shorelines were prepared, DSAS was used to create a baseline, from which transects were cast perpendicular to the shoreline at regular intervals. It is a must to include all vector data into a personal geodatabase by giving correct parameters. The transect spacing and length were adjusted based on the specific geomorphological characteristics of the study area and by considering the

pattern and direction of shorelines to optimize the analysis. The shorelines gathered from 2004, 2015, and 2021 exported into shape file (.shp) and after merging all three shorelines, saved in a personal geo-database called 'Shoreline'. The created baseline (onshore) also added to a personal geo-database called 'Baseline'. Using the shoreline and baseline data available in the personal geo database, a transect layer was created using DSAS tool at 100 meter intervals by considering the lengths of shorelines with a smoothing distance of 1,000 meters. All the data layers were projected in Universal Transverse Mercator (WGS 1984 / UTM zone 44N) projection. Positive accretion and negative erosion were observed in the rates of shoreline variability. Major statistical outcomes of DSAS such as net Shoreline Movement (NSM), Shoreline Change Envelope (SCE), Endpoint Rate (EPR) are used by the researcher for the interpretation.

The Net Shoreline Movement Equation is used for each transect or hypothetical line that crosses a shoreline perpendicularly, NSM summarises the actual distance between the oldest and youngest shoreline (Thasarathan, N. et al, 2023).

$$NSM = (d_{2004} - d_{2021}) \text{ m}$$

Equation 1: Net Shoreline Movement Calculation

The End Point Rate (EPR) calculated by dividing the distance of shoreline movement by the time elapsed between the oldest and the most recent shoreline.

$$EPR = \frac{d_{2021} - d_{2004}}{t_{2021} - t_{2004}} \text{ m/year.}$$

Equation 2: End Point Rate Calculation

The shoreline change envelope (SCE) reports a distance (in meters), not a rate. The SCE value represents the largest distance between all coastlines intersecting a given transect. The value for SCE is always positive,

since there is no absolute distance sign between two coastlines (USGS, 2018)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Long-term shoreline changes in the study area calculated by extracting shoreline proxy positions from seventeen years between 2004 and 2021 using automated methods, after which the DSAS was used to calculate and visualize the amounts and rates of change between the different shoreline positions.

The net shoreline movement (NSM), which represents the total horizontal shoreline change between 2004 and 2021 is shown in figure 2. This illustrates the changes in the form of a chart where varying amounts of total erosions or accretions occurred, along with a graph showing the exact amount of NSM at each 150m transect. The results in Figure 02 show that much of the study area has experienced both negative and positive NSM over the studied period.

Figure 2: NSM over 17 years

Overall, 45.6% of the study area has experienced positive NSM with an average movement of 41.5m. The greatest NSM was 2,314.38m and occurred in the Colombo district coastal area in the western coast due to the Port City project, while the greatest advanced (landward) movement was -305m. Around, 27.2% of the study area has experienced negative NSM with an average movement of -29.8m. This erosion occurred mainly in some parts of the eastern coastline, western coastal area as well as in the south-western coastal area. Moreover, within the total transects, 27.2% of transects showed no detectable change (Table 1).

Table 1: Summary of Erosion and Accretion Statistics

Net Erosion (%)	Maximum Erosion	Net Accretion (%)	Maximum Accretion
27.2%	305.96m	45.5%	2314.38m

In addition to the NSM, the Shoreline Change Envelope (SCE), which is the greatest distance between shorelines regardless of time and direction, was computed. Even though, the SCE shows more variability and dynamics of shoreline movement. Most of the shoreline transects has happened due to significant man made changes and not due to natural causes over the studied period. Table 2 summarises the SCE statistics that correspond to the maximum and minimum NSM of 2314.38m and -305.96m respectively.

Table 2: Summary of Shoreline Change Envelope (SCE) Statistics

Average	Maximum	Minimum
39.77	2314.38	305.96

DSAS calculates three different statistics to represent the rate of horizontal shoreline change over time (m/yr). These are the End Point Rate (EPR), the Linear Regression Rate (LRR) and the Weighted Linear Regression Rate (WLR); where the EPR is simply the NSM divided by the total period (17 years). Hence, the maximum EPR was the NSM value of 2,314.38m divided by 17 years, which equates to 135.7m/yr. Similar to the NSM results, 27.2% of the study site transects have negative rates (erosion), while 45.5% have positive rates (accretion). The maximum EPR was the NSM value of -185.98m divided by 17 years, which equates to -30.86m/yr. These statistics are summarised in Table 3 and Table 04, respectively.

Table 3: Summary of Accretion Rates

Average Accretion Rate	Percent of Positive Rates (Statistically Significant) (%)	Maximum Rate of Accretion
2.6 ±5.8	45.5%	135.7 ±11.6

Table 4: Summary of Erosion Rates

Average Erosion Rate	Percent of Negative Rates (Statistically Significant) (%)	Maximum Rate of Erosion
-1 ±2	27.2%	-30.8 ±5.5

The results of the coastal change analysis using Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) over the study period of 17 years of long-term, the coastal change measurement and the rate, highlight significant patterns of coastal dynamics that have critical implications for coastal management and planning. According to the results, 27.2% of the transition zones show an average erosion of -29.8m per year. This rate is substantial for a small island like Sri Lanka. Maximum erosions are observed especially in the northern, eastern, western and southern parts of Sri Lanka and the same was confirmed by the previous studies. These areas are highly vulnerable to wave action, natural disasters, human activities and sea level rise.

According to the study, erosions are lesser in north eastern and north western coast. Iranawila beach is also mostly threatened due to beach erosion in Puttalam district. In 2010 at Oluvil Harbour area, severe impact of coastal erosion extended to Saindamarudu, covering 16 km north of Oluvil Harbour, in which the country lost more than 100m of coastal strip in the study period. Furthermore, due to flood control measures in ‘Kalu Ganga’ in estuary by

expanding 2017, the barrier beach of Kalutara (Kalido beach) has been destroyed. These flood control efforts resulted in severe erosion that spread over 3km, passing the Tangerine Beach Hotel and Royal Palm Beach Hotel. Moreover, a sand bar is developing in a different orientation at the ‘Kalu Ganga’ river estuary and due to this situation, direct waves and river flow affected the island, and about 100 m of land washed away along the coast of the island. Further, Galle in the southern coast is one of the most vulnerable areas of erosion. Hikkaduwa and Habaraduwa are the most vulnerable of the erosion identified on the South coast. In addition, Trincomalee and Batticaloa have minor erosion conditions due to regional seasonal changes. Moreover, as shown in Figure 03, it can be observed that the country is losing a strip of land along the Oluvil beach.

Figure 3: Coastal Erosion in the Oluvil Coastline

Coastal accretions are important due to formation of new lands; enhance coastal protection by buffering against storm surges and erosion, and support habitats for diverse marine and terrestrial life. According to the study, most of the southern and western parts of Sri Lanka taking averaging accretion as a result from reduced wave energy due to sediment deposition from upstream systems and the presence of natural breakwaters. The main changes of shoreline accretion can be identified in the Colombo Port City Project, Hambantota Port and other anthropogenic structures. According to the results of this study, 45% transects records beach accretion

including, the Port City project. Along with the analysis data, 45% has been recorded in terms of beach accretion. Although the amounts have been recorded as 45%, natural beach accretions are mainly identified in south of Oluvil harbour and around Kalpitiya and minor accretions notably taken place in the north eastern coast. This suggests that these areas can act as sediment sources for eroded zones if sustainable sediment management practices are instituted. Additionally, these available lands can be utilised for the development, recreational purposes by enhancing the security of local economies and communities.

The results of this study support the hypothesis and stress the necessity of constant observation and evaluation of shoreline changes to develop effective strategies for coastal security. Thus, erosion and accretion analysis help stakeholders to decide which areas require the most attention and funds and which regions should be focused on to safeguard infrastructure and community from potential natural disasters such as flooding, storm surges to improve the safety of inhabitants of coastal areas. The future studies should encompass long-term changes and incorporate socio-economic aspects in order to analyse the effects of shoreline shift on habitats and their security while providing safe and sustainable coastal environment.

Figure 4: Net Shoreline Movements around the main island of Sri Lanka and few districts

CONCLUSION

This paper compared shoreline changes of the coastline of the Sri Lanka in the period of 2004 - 2021 and demonstrated net shoreline changes during the studied period. According to a coastal erosion trend analysis carried out by Abeykoon L.C.K et al., 2021 covering the 2005-2019 period, focused on the Western and Northwestern provinces revealing average coastal erosion rates of -1.21 ± 0.04 m yr⁻¹ in Kalutara, -0.54 ± 0.63 m yr⁻¹ in Colombo, and -0.7 ± 0.58 m yr⁻¹ in Gampaha district respectively. Puttalam district showed a 0.26 ± 0.07 m yr⁻¹ average accretion rate, while the highest accretion rate (0.95 ± 0.58 m yr⁻¹) was evident in the coastal region of Wilpattu National Park, an area that has few anthropogenic interventions.

The study results found that the application of hard structures to mitigate the effect of coastal erosion has increased within the past 17 years. According to the Coastal Zone and Coastal Resource Management Plan 2024 - 2029 of Coastal Conservation Department, by the end of 2019, the country mainly used revetments up to 23,554 m in length (occupying 9.05% of the total study area), consisting of 18,960 m in the Western province (7.29%) and 4,594 m in the Northwestern province (1.76%). The Western province has applied more hard structures at a higher rate than the Northwestern province due to mega-development projects.

Using multi-temporal satellite images acquired over a 17-year period (between 2004 and 2021), shoreline dynamics along the coastline stretch of Sri Lanka (main island) was extensively investigated. The analysis revealed that some of the evaluated areas were experiencing significant erosions as well as accretions. The areas around the Puttalam, Galle, Matara, Gampaha (Pamunugama), Hambantota, Ampara, Batticaloa, Trincomalee (the canyon in the Trincomalee Bay traps most of the sediment supplied by the Mahaweli river), and Jaffna (Vankalai and Kondachikudah) are high erosion risk zones. According to the research findings and the literature of the previous studies in the specific areas, natural reasons such as loss of sand due to breaching and wash-over of a sand berm, offshore sand loss during extreme wave and storm surge conditions, loss of sand due to presence of canyons, deposition of sand at sand spits and dunes, loss of coastal vegetation, tsunami, cyclones and other episodic events, and Sea level rise accelerate the erosion.

In contrast, high threatening anthropogenic factors to the coastline that have identified in the study are beach sand mining, river sand mining, construction of buildings and other structures too close to the beach and on sand dunes, breaching sandbars at river and lagoon outlets and construction of unplanned or poorly planned rigid coastal structures, etc. It can be seen that accretion processes are taking

place due to the natural flows of the major rivers in the study area and due to the activities of illegal sand mining in the respective rivers. Accordingly, the conclusions derived from this study can be applied to improve the future stability of the identified area and the construction of appropriate coastal structures in the entire coastal region of Sri Lanka. In view of this, they do enrich the knowledge on coastal security challenges emanating from coast erosion and sedimentation, hence safeguarding critical infrastructure, human dwellings and sensitive ecosystems that embrace the coastal regions. It is no doubt, the experiences derived from this study shall assist future Coastal Zone Management in the formulation of policies and measures to protect regions vulnerable to erosion and sedimentation, thereby achieving long term security and coastal resilience for the people of Sri Lanka.

Therefore, there is a need to emphasise the limitations and future research directions of this coastal study. Using 30 m resolution Landsat images, which are available free data, some constraints are encountered in the research and those constraints have affected the accuracy. Especially in cases related to location, a source (Google Earth Pro) or its authenticity should be confirmed. Integrating other data sources such as drone imagery, aerial photography or light detection and ranging (LiDAR) data can be explored to improve the accuracy of coastal mapping and expand detection. In addition, advances in satellite technology may provide higher resolution images enabling more detailed, accurate analyses in the future, and such studies will be more likely to collect data using present information. Furthermore, the researcher hopes that this research will serve as a basis for future research in the field, for policymaking and security confirmations in related sectors, to have a basic understanding of coastal dynamics, and to find valuable discoveries by minimizing the limitations to be faced. It will guide future researchers in designing and conducting studies that are more informative and focused on enhancing coastal security.

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